

EU4Digital

Data Cubes

A pragmatic and painless introduction

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EaPEC 2019

Yerevan, Armenia

Agenda

1. The challenge
2. Defining Datacubes
3. Examples: Software Frameworks + Data + Webaccess
4. Conclusion

The Challenge

- **New generations of EO satellites are creating increasingly significant volumes of data** with such comprehensive global coverage that for many applications, **the lack of data is no longer a limiting factor.**
- **Instead, already available EO satellite data is underutilised despite modern computing and analysis infrastructures.**
- **Now, the challenge is in providing the proper connections between data, applications and users.**
- **The data management and analysis challenges arising from the huge increase in data volumes can be overcome with new computing infrastructures, technologies and data architectures.**

What is a Datacube ?

- A **datacube** is a **massive multi-dimensional array** of raster/gridded data.
- Satellite image timeseries: Latitude and Longitude coordinates and time; data would be a pixel at a given space/time coordinate as taken by the satellite.
- “massive”: the digital memory footprint exceeds significantly the main memory resources of a desktop or server machine.
- For **remote sensing data providers**, datacubes can **streamline the management and distribution of data** streams coming from satellite constellations.
- For **users of remote sensing data**,
 - datacubes simplify internet-based access to the data,
 - provide access in an analysis-ready way and
 - foster an active and engaged **global community of contributors**.

Mount Whitney,
Kalifornien (2009-2011)
Quicklooks: RapidEye AG

Datacubes connect data providers and users, by standards and services

Data Producers

Image Acquisition Planning /
Tasking / Downlink / Processing

Transfer Service
Standards

Software
Systems

End Users
Data
Consumers

Datacubes: Technical perspective

Array RDBMS and OLAP

Array RDBMS

http://icon-park.com/imagefiles/rubiks_cube_gray.png

An **OLAP cube** is a multi-dimensional array of data. Online analytical processing (OLAP) is a **computer-based technique of analyzing data to look for insights**. [Wikipedia]

Array database management systems (DBMSs)

provide database services specifically for arrays , that is: homogeneous collections of data items, sitting on a regular grid of one, two, or more dimensions. [...] Such arrays tend to be Big Data, with single objects frequently ranging into Terabyte and soon Petabyte sizes; for example, today's earth and space observation archives typically grow by Terabytes a day. Array databases aim at offering flexible, scalable storage and retrieval on this information category.

https://galaktika-soft.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/olap_operations.jpg

Datacubes Functionalities

Datacubes shall... [DatacubeManifesto]

http://kahlua.eecs.jacobs-university.de/~earthserver/sites/default/files/cube-wallpaper_mr.jpg

1. ..support **gridded data** of at least one through four spatial, temporal, or other dimensions
2. ..**treat all axes alike**, irrespective of an axis having a spatial, temporal, or other semantics.
3. ..allow **efficient trimming and slicing** along any number of axes from a datacube in a single request.
4. ..convey similar **extraction performance** along any datacube axis.
5. ..allow **adaptive partitioning**, invisible to the user when performing access and analysis
6. support a language **allowing clients** to submit simple as well as composite extraction, processing, filtering, and fusion **tasks in an ad-hoc fashion**

https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web_Coverage_Service

Standards and Services

“Availability of datacube standards and tools is heralding a new era of service quality and, ultimately, better data insights.”
 [Datacube Manifesto]

Internet-standards to access Datacubes are defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC):

- OGC Coverage Implementation Schema (ICS)
- OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS)
- OGC Web Coverage Processing Services(WCPS)

The OGC® Web Coverage Service Interface Standard enables access to coverages (satellite images, elevation data, etc.) held in diverse data repositories.

https://live.osgeo.org/archive/10.5/de/standards/wcs_overview.html

Applications and Tools for Users: High Level View

Applications and Tools for Users: Workflow Example

The European Data Cube Facility Service high-level architecture

Initiatives, Services and Projects

OPEN DATA CUBE

- The **Open Data Cube (ODC) initiative** seeks to provide a data architecture solution that has value to its global users and increases the impact of EO satellite data.
- The **Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS)** is a founding partner of ODC.
- ODC is a **non-profit, open source project (Apache 2.0 Licence)**.
- This project was born out of the work done under the "Unlocking the Landsat Archive" and the Australian Geoscience Data Cube (AGDC) projects.

DOI: 10.1109/
IGARSS.2018.8517694

OPEN DATA CUBE

Tools and Applications

Web-based User Interface

Open Data Cube Home Data Cube Manager Tools Task Manager Submit Feedback Logged in as: briem Logout

Welcome to the Open Data Cube

ODC is using the power of the Open Data Cube to help address the needs of satellite data users, giving them a better picture of their land resources and land change.

- Ease of use and access to satellite-based data
- Multiple output interoperability and spatial consistency
- Use of "Analysis Ready" Data Products
- A Shift in Paradigm from Scenes to Pixels

<http://tinyurl.com/datacubeui>

- 16 sample data cubes + 10 common applications
- Free and Open, easy-to-use, menu-driven, GIS tool
- Applications focused on Landsat data
- GeoTIFF outputs, animations, pixel drill

Jupyter Python Notebook Hub

There are 6 core notebooks (cloud statistics, custom mosaics, water extent, spectral products, land change, vegetation phenology) with You-Tube videos. Many more algorithms are under development and testing.

How can we use the Open Data Cube?

- **Cloud-free Mosaics:** Recent Pixel, Median, Geomedian, Max-NDVI
- **Spectral Indices:** NDVI, NDBI, NDSI, NDWI, SAVI, EVI, Fractional Cover
- **Land Classification:** K-Means, Random Forest, FAO 8-class decision tree
- **Water:** Landsat WOFs (Australia), Sentinel-1 WASARD (NASA), Landsat Water Quality (Australia) - Total Suspended Matter
- **Land Change:** Spectral Threshold Anomaly, Coastal Change, PyCCD (USGS)

https://static.wixstatic.com/media/8959d6_d66ba5dab5534f96bd798ce2e23ee6ca~mv2.png/v1/fill/w_210,h_141,al_c,q_80,usm_0.66_1.00_0.01/f9d4ea_01051dcf29714909b496a364f2b3fcd9__webp

European Data Cube Facility Project [2019-2021]

- The European Data Cube Facility service is providing fast access to a considerable amount of EO information from instrument data up to environmental variables and in order to establish a “bridge from Space to Applications”.
- It exploits the team experience to access EO data from the cloud such as DIAS, avoiding at maximum data replication and offering users the possibility to apply their own algorithm and data transformations.
- The project also contributes to the interoperability activities in the related domain to maximize the service capabilities and foster federation of similar initiatives worldwide.
- <https://eo4society.esa.int/projects/european-data-cube-facility/>

We were selected by EARSC as the
European EO Company of the Year 2018!

**EUROPEAN EO COMPANY
OF THE YEAR 2018**

EARSC

European Association
of Remote Sensing
Companies

CLOUD API FOR SATELLITE IMAGERY

Browse. Pick. Enhance. Expose.

EXPLORE HUB

REQUEST TRIAL

What do we do?

We make satellite data (Sentinels, Landsat and other providers) easily accessible for you to be browsed or analyzed, within our cloud GIS or within your own environment.

Get satellite imagery on your table without worrying about synchronization issues, storage, processing, de-compression algorithms, meta-data or sensor bands.

Sentinel Hub: Tools and Applications

Open EO data - Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Landsat, etc.

Commercial EO data - WorldWind, GeoEye,...

Aerial imagery (drone, plane)

Other raster data

WMTS

WMS

WCS

API

Machine learning

Cloud GIS

Web / Mobile apps

Desktop (QGIS,, ArcGIS...)

Scripting (R, Python, ENVI...)

<http://www.bigdatacube.org/>

Under the lead of [Jacobs University](#), The [BigDataCube](#) project is developing flexible and scalable services for massive spatio-temporal Earth Observation (EO) data, offered as datacubes. This paradigm replaces the millions of EO files by a few massive multi-dimensional space/time objects, such as 3D image timeseries and 4D weather forecast cubes. This way, raster data get ready for spatio-temporal analysis in the large. Goal of [BigDataCube](#) is to enhance access to value-adding services supporting collaboration across disciplinary and geographical boundaries for industry and research. The massively simplified Big Data handling benefits users of existing services as well as new businesses, e.g., in agro-informatics: they don't need to develop or deploy complex technology and manage all data, but can use data readily, thereby freeing resources for their core business. Hence, on the BigDataCube platform novel, specialized services can be established by third parties in a fast, flexible, and scalable manner.

Concretely, the project deploys the European Datacube engine, [rasdaman](#), in two infrastructures:

- The commercial hosted processing environment of [cloudeo](#). Novel datacube access control and quota will safely handle both free and proprietary data provided by Intermap and PlanetObserver.
- The public service of [CODE-DE](#), the German Copernicus hub, thereby complementing the batch-oriented Hadoop service with interactive extraction and processing along the paradigm of "*any query, any time, on any size*". [DLR Bremen](#) will exemplarily establish a weather and ocean analytics tool based on [rasdaman](#).

Further, CODE-DE and cloudeo services will be federated, allowing users to combine datacubes from both services without the need for downloading them first.

www.code-de.org/en

The Copernicus Data and Exploitation Platform – Deutschland (CODE-DE) is the German entry point to the EU Copernicus Sentinel Satellite Systems, their data products and the products of the Copernicus Services.

Next to that CODE-DE will offer for specific users processing facilities on the platform.

DATASETS >

Sentinel-1

Sentinel-2

Sea & Wind State

Germany NDVI

CLIENTS >

Jupyter Notebook

WMS

WCS

WCPS

FUNCTIONS >

Services Federation

Color Palette Table

Sea & Wind Prediction

Sea State

Wind Speed

Polygon Clipping

www.bigdatacube.org

Conclusion: Standing on the shoulders of ... Standards and Services

The future is already here – it's just not very evenly distributed.

[William Gibson]

Thanks for Listening !

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